

PAST TENSE IN UZBEK, RUSSIAN AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

Usanova Qademay Muratbay qizi

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
The Faculty of Turkic languages is a student of
Uzbek language direction 2 in foreign language groups.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11172779>

Abstract.

In this article, the comparison of the verb word category in Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the past tense form of the verb, their similarities and differences were studied.

Keywords: verb word category, grammatical category, degree, declension, tense, person-number, affix, declension, incomplete verb, adjective, case.

Verb-the richest in grammatical categories in all 3 languages, grammatical nature is the most complex category. Words belonging to the verb word category indicate the process.

The action, state meaning of a verb is expressed through its special grammatical categories. The verb has grammatical categories like rank – zalog – da'reje, mile – naklonenie – meyl, tense – Vremya – Ma'ha'l, person and son – liso I chislo – bet Ha'm san in all 3 languages.

The verb stands out among all word categories in terms of its versatility in meaning, its richness in grammatical categories, forms, as well as its most important place in the composition of the sentence. The Russian linguist academician Peshkovsky was certainly right when he said: "when word categories are compared to planets, the verb is the sun among them." The use of the verb as a central clause in Uzbek also proves this¹.

The present tense in Uzbek differs from the past tense in the near past tense, the long past tense, the past tense in the narrative verb, the past tense in the continuation verb and the past tense in the target verb, each of which has its own means of expression. Adding and Tusing the –di affix to the near past tense verb stem, adding and Tusing the long past tense adjectival adjectival-gan affix, (edi, as a result of the conjugation of incomplete verbs with the verb form receiving the – gan affix), adding and Tusing the inflected –B(ib) affix to the past tense narrative verb stem, adding and Tusing the past tense continuation verb –(A)to the adjective was incomplete verb conjugation, to the verb stem – by adding the affix moqda, the verb edi incomplete is expressed by conjugating and adding the affix – moqchi to the past tense target verb stem as well as by adding the affix edi incomplete verb tousling or – to the next tense adjectival verb Edi tousled and conjugated.

The past tense form in Russian is made by adding the suffix –L - to the infinitive base of verbs. This verb adjusts in unity according to the rod of the word it connects to, but is not voiced in the person. For example: the word chitat mujskoy rod will be ya chital in person I, Ti chital in person II, and on chital in person III; and jensky rod will have ya chitala in person I, Ti chitala in person II, and mother chitala in person III, that is, it adapts according to the rod of the word to which it is connected, but does not This is formed by adding the plural –I affix of

¹ Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent. 2006. – B. 110.

the tense affix. In such a situation, it does not change depending on the rods and is not tousel on individuals. For example: Mi chitali (we read) . VI chitali (you read). Like Oni chitali (they read).

In Karakalpak, past tense forms of the verb indicate that the work-action is worked or not before the time of speaking. Semantic types of past tense forms are very widely used in the facts of the current Karakalpak literary language. It is divided into 8 groups of meanings, depending on the semantic contradictions of the past tense². 1. The exact past tense-work-indicates that the action took place clearly, before the moment of speaking, whether it was worked or not. In this, the work-movement is attended to by the speaker himself or reports the events that he clearly sees, knows. 2. The indefinite past tense-hol is expressed through the addition of person -number affixes to the verb-p,-ip/-ip form. For example: aytippan, aytipsan', as aytipti. 3. The resultant past tense-- -Ghan/-gen (- qan/ - ken) denotes the arrival of the formal adjective and the same adjective with affixes in the person-number. For example: alganman, algansan', Algan. 4. The preceding Past Tense is expressed by the addition of an incomplete verb that is in the present kelar form of the--Khan/-gen formal adjective and the-A/ - e, - y+di definite article. For example: Kuzma Baradin men Ju'z khaninin ' Aris patšasina gasip aliw Erza qilğaninin, Sanda qaraqalpaqtin'da some biyelerinin' erzi etgeninin bile di eken (T. Q.). 5. The definite preceding tense - - - G'an / -gen is made by the addition of an incomplete verb that was tousel in 3 persons to the formal adjective and-ip,- ip, - P-form hol verb. For example: Bul nanlar bizlerdin' bir ha'pte burin orghan biydiyimizdin'inan jabqaran. 6. The unfinished past tense was - - tughin,-ar/-er/,- r,-mas/- mes, (- i/ - i) made through forms such as wshi/wshi edi. For example: Ha'r Ku'ni otirip ketiw ushin bizikine Qartabay gharri keletugin (s.A.). 7. The next-Past Tense - is made by the addition of the verb edi incomplete to the forms of the next tense adjective -jaq, the target pronoun -maqshi/-mekshi, and the action noun -iw/-iw,- W. For example: Balalardin ' arasi nan elge bashi tayarlap bersen'iz, U'yretsen'z dep aytpaqshi Idi (t. Q.). 8. The continuous past tense -the continuous form of the Past Tense is made by adding the case-denoting verbs jatir, otir, tur, Ju'r to the suffix-maqta/ - mekte iwda/ - iwde to the verbs of the present tense, ekan incomplete verbs. For example: Tek ashiwli's eye was Ghana baigha qadalmaqta (S.X.).

In Russian, the form of the past tense from some verbs is made differently. 1. The infinitive form is made from verbs ending in-STI,-zti without the suffix-L, the mujskoy rod form of the past tense of NES -Ti, nesu, vez-Ti, vezu. In this, it is equal to the base itself. I.e. NES - Ti-on Nyos, vez - ti-ti vyo. 2. The singular form of the verb mujskoy rod, which ends with the infinitive form -CH, is made by adding the vowel K(G) to the verb base³. For example: Pech - Ti pyok, berech - Ya BEREG, pomoch - on pomog. In the singular form of the jensky and sredny rods, as well as in the plural, the suffix -L and the corresponding ending are added . For example: Mat Pek-l-a, BEREG-l-a, pomog-l-a.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that the meanings of past tense forms in Uzbek are given in Russian by the past tense form, which is made of both completed and unfinished types of verbs. The meaning groups of past tense forms in Uzbek are 6, and in Karakalpak the meaning groups of past tense are 8. The differences here are that the meaning groups of past tense forms in the Karakalpak language are numerous, and the meanings they

² Da'wletov A va boshqalar. Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. - No'kis, 2010. - B. 167.

³ Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent,1965. - B. 65.

mean are also different. Therefore, in Russian they are given with various suffixes. In Uzbek, it is given in the same 6 forms. Learning languages by analogy will be easy and fun for any language learner. It is sure to increase, of course, even the craving for language learning.

References:

1. Azizov O va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti.1965.
2. O.Azizov va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 1986.
3. Bekbergenov A. Rus ha'm qaraqalpaq tillerinin' salistirmali grammatikasi. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2006
4. Da'wletov A va boshqalar Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2010.
5. Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 2006.